

Self-Efficacy Of Xi Standard Students And Their Academic Achievement

Dr.S.Akila

Assistant Professor of Biological Science (Education)
Government College of Education for Women, Coimbatore-1

Corresponding author- Dr.S.Akila

Abstract

The present investigation focuses on the study of Self-efficacy of XI standard students and their academic achievement. The survey method was adopted in this present study. In this study, 250 higher secondary students were taken as sample through the Stratified random sampling technique. Mean, standard deviation, 't'-test, F-test and Post ANOVA and correlational analysis were used to analyse the data. The results revealed that there is significant correlation between Self-efficacy and Academic Achievement of XI standard students.

Self-Efficacy

Self-efficacy is the belief of we have in our own abilities, specifically our ability to meet the challenges ahead of us and complete a task successfully refers to overall belief in our ability to succeed, but there are many more specific forms of self-efficacy as well.

Self-efficacy affects every area of human endeavor by determining the beliefs a person holds regarding their power to affect situations, it strongly influences both the power a person actually has to face challenges competently and the choices a person most is likely to make. These effects are particularly apparent, compelling, with regard to behaviors affecting health.

Definitions Of Self-Efficacy

According to **Albert Bandura** perceived self-efficacy as people's judgment of their capabilities to organize and execute courses of action required to attain designation performances. It is concerned not with the skills one has but with the judgments of what one can do with whatever skills one possesses.

According to **Pajares (1996)** defined self-efficacy in terms of individual's perceived capacities to attain designated type of performance and to achieve specific results.

Importance Of Self-Efficacy

The students with a strong sense of self-efficacy believe they can accomplish even difficult tasks. In the face of impending failure, these students increase and sustain their efforts to be successful. They are approach difficulty or threatening situations with confidence that they have control over them. Developing efficacy beliefs in the classroom is a great place to start. We all see our students struggle with motivation. Self-efficacy can be adrenaline for motivation. Student who are confident, free from stress show a greater propensity to be motivated. In class, allow students more self-observation, self-judgment and self-reaction time. Carefully, schedule proximal goals. The more distant the goal, the more students lose the benefit of

self-efficacy. Self-efficacy increases as students note progress, attain goals, and set new challenges.

Significance Of The Study

Self – efficacy should be emphasized by every individual to ensure things to do can be done steadily and confidently. It provide useful information for teachers. Students would be able to lay out specific learning strategies and verbalize them. would be able to exploit their capacities to execute behavior necessary to provide specific performance attainments and leverage on their ability to exert control over ones own motivation behavior and social environment. It is more attention to the self-efficacy. Present study stems from the fact that it explores. The correlation between self- efficacy and student's academic achievement.

Objectives Of The Study

1. To find out whether there is significant difference between male and female XI Standard Students in their Self-efficacy.
2. To find out whether there is significant difference between rural and urban XI Standard Students in their Self-efficacy.
3. To find out whether there is significant difference between Tamil and English medium XI Standard Students in their Self-efficacy.
4. To find out whether there is significant correlation between self-efficacy and academic achievement.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There is no significant difference between Male and Female XI Standard Students in their Self-efficacy.
2. There is no significant difference between Rural and Urban XI Standard Students in their Self-efficacy.
3. There is no significant difference between Tamil and English medium XI Standard Students in their Self-efficacy.
4. There is no significant correlation between Self-efficacy and Academic Achievement of XI Standard Students.

Methodology

Survey method was used by the investigator for this Study. Stratified random sampling technique is used for selecting samples for this study. The sample consists of 250, XI standard students studying in various Schools in Coimbatore

district. The tool used in this investigation was Self-efficacy inventory constructed and Standardized by the investigator.

Data Analysis Null hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between male and female of XI Standard students in their self-efficacy.

Table 1: Self-efficacy of XI Standard Students based on Gender

Gender	No. of students	Mean	Standard deviation	Calculated 't' value	Table value	Remark at 5% level of significance
Male	132	63.37	6.283	4.105	1.96	Significant
Female	118	67.27	8.438			

From the above table 4.3 evidence that the 't' value of self-efficacy score of male and female XI standard students is 4.105 which is significant at 5% level. It indicates male and female students differ significantly on the level of self-efficacy. Further the mean scores reveal that male students (6.283) and female students (8.438) does not show significant difference Hence null hypothesis, "There

is significant difference between male and female XI standard students in their self-efficacy" is rejected. It may, therefore, be concluded that the male and female students show statistically significance of difference in their self-efficacy.

Null hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between rural and urban XI standard students in their Self-efficacy.

Table 2: Self-efficacy of XI Standard Students based on Locality

Locality of the school	N	Mean	S.D	Calculated 't' value	Table value	Remark at 5% level
Rural	132	65.82	6.437	1.311	1.96	Not significant
Urban	118	64.53	8.731			

From the above table 4.4 evidence that the 't' value of self-efficacy score of rural and urban XI standard students is 1.311 which is not significant at 5% level. The Mean score of rural students is 65.82 and urban students are 64.53 which shows that there is a slight difference in their mean scores. Hence null hypothesis is accepted "There is no significant

difference between rural and urban XI standard students in their self-efficacy".

Null hypothesis 3

There is no significant difference between Tamil and English medium XI standard students in their self-efficacy.

Table 3: Self-efficacy of XI Standard Students based on Medium

Medium of instruction	N	Mean	S.D	Calculated 't' value	Table value	Remark at 5% level
Tamil	130	64.16	6.752	2.270	1.96	Significant
English	120	66.35	8.336			

From the above table 4.5 evidence that the 't' value of self-efficacy score of Tamil and English medium XI standard students is 2.270 which is significant at 5% level. It indicates tamil and English medium students differ significantly on the level of self-efficacy. Further the mean scores reveal that Tamil

medium students (6.752) and English medium students (8.336) does not show significant difference. Hence null hypothesis, "There is significant difference between Tamil and English medium XI standard students in their self-efficacy" is rejected. It may, therefore, be concluded that the tamil and English medium students show

statistically significance of difference in their self-efficacy.

There is no significant correlation between Self-efficacy and Academic Achievement of XI standard students.

Null hypothesis 4

Table 4: Correlation between Self-efficacy and academic achievement of XI Standard Students

Correlation	ΣX^2	ΣY^2	Σxy	Calculated 't' Value	Remarks
Self-efficacy and Academic Achievement	14449.762884	2017374.41538	57339.64494	0.347	Significant

From the above table, it is inferred that there is significant correlation between Self-efficacy and Academic Achievement of XI Standard students. The calculated correlation value (0.347) is greater than the table value (0.088) at 5% level of significance. Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is significant correlation between Self-efficacy and Academic Achievement of IX standard students

Recommendations

Teacher should promote activity oriented classrooms and provide opportunities for a wide range of communicative experiences. Learners should be given plenty of opportunities to explain their ideas to their team mates and to lead the discussion. Teaching struggling learners to make greater efforts. Linking new work to recent success. Reinforcing effort and persistence Student's self-efficacy should be cultivated routinely through activities to become competent decision makers in the future.

Conclusion

The purpose of the present investigation was to study the self-efficacy of XI standard students and their Academic Achievement. Self-efficacy is one of the most influential factors for learning, it appears to be very important for the teacher to help students develop their self-efficacy. Teachers can enhance the level of student's efficacy through various feasible teaching techniques. Efforts should be made to enhance the level of self-efficacy so that academic achievement can be improved especially of those students who have reported low academic achievement. Findings can be proven effective for the students in motivating developing positive attitude, ensuring low of readiness, developing skill, shaping leadership quality making realized and focused towards academic activities.

References

1. Bhatnagar, R.P. (2005). Reading in methodology of research in education. Meerut: R.Lall Book Depot.
2. Kothari, C.R. (2004). Research Methodology (2nd ed). New Delhi: New Age International Publishers Pvt.Ltd.

3. Singh and Kulbir Sinhu. (1984). Methodology of research in education. New Delhi: Sterling Publishers Pvt Ltd.
4. Mohammad Hasan, Mohammad Parvez (2019). Effect of Self-Efficacy, Gender and Locale on the Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students. International Journal of Scientific Research and Reviews. Vol 8(2), 1881-1892
5. Amit Ahuja (2016). A study of self-efficacy among secondary school students in relation to educational aspiration and academic achievement. An international journal of education and applied social sciences.
6. <https://www.researchgate.net>
7. <https://www.semanticscholar.com>
8. <https://www.researchjournal.com>
9. <https://www.academiaedu.com>